

Analysis on Crack Propagation in Ti-6Al-4V Skin under Tensile Loading

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Received: September 21, 2014, Accepted: October 28, 2014, Published: October 28, 2014.

ABSTRACT

The main objective of current work is to investigate how a crack propagates and grows in a typical Ti-6Al-4V material plate. By using the finite element method software (ANSYS13) were used to simulate crack growth and to compute the stresses and the stress-intensity factor. A specific plate design was selected and a corner crack was investigated, since engineers often detect this type of crack in plates. The VonMises stress near the crack tip is compared against the yield strength of the material. Under the tensile loading i.e in Mode-I the stress-intensity factor is compared against the material's fracture toughness. The results show that the plate can tolerate minute cracks in the structure. The fatigue strength of the structure is recommended to be assessed in the future.

Keywords: Crack Propagation, Stress Intensity Factor, Tensile loading and Flaw size.

INTRODUCTION

According to Bently and Muszynska [1], in the 70s and till the beginning of the 80s, at least 28 shaft failures due to cracks were registered in the USA energy industry. Thus, since the 80s, the interest of researchers to characterize structures containing cracks is growing remarkably. The problem of determination of the behavior of cracked structures has been tackled with for a long time. And the fact that a crack presence or a local defect in a structural member introduces a local flexibility that arrests its vibration response was known long ago. This local flexibility is related to the strain energy concentration in the vicinity of the crack [3].

Airliners progressively more demand for high performance and fuel-efficient aircrafts due to the increasing gasoline price. In order to meet the market needs, original equipment manufacturers are developing smaller and lighter aircraft engines. Industry analysts are expecting the engine components in the next decades to be very space efficient [4]. As a result, light but high strength materials are very valuable and competitively sourced to reduce weight and cost in manufacturing aircraft engine. Aero engine designers design brackets in various shapes and sizes for mounting bleed air ducting, starter air duct, fuel lines and hydraulic lines to the engine core. One can find more than one hundred mounting points in an engine [5].

Any crack found in a skin may cause the ducting to become unstable during a mission, and thus induce high cycle fatigue load on the overall major structures and shorten the structures life. From the economic standpoint, it is a cost saving strategy to replace brackets before they are completely damaged due to replacing broken brackets mitigates the risk of damaging other major components, such as the ducting, which are more costly to replace. Besides, replacing a bracket before it completely breaks

can avoid many engineering catastrophes and save many lives [6].

Nickel-based alloys such as Inconel 718 and Inconel 625 are widely used in aerospace industry for ducting and brackets. However according to Honnorat [4], only titanium alloys could satisfy the requirement and the increasing demand for high strength per weight materials that needed for a wide range of components. According to the unknown author on World Wide Web, Wikipedia, many aircraft use titanium due to their high tensile strength to density ratio, high corrosion resistance, fatigue resistance, high crack resistance, and ability to withstand moderately high temperatures without creeping.

According to Immarigeon *et al* [5] titanium-based alloys are widely used in aerospace applications because the material can increase the strength-to-weight ratio in structures and provide heat resistance with weight savings. Their relatively low density decreases the magnitude of vibration problems. However, the significant weight savings permitted by these titanium application developments generated specific drawbacks that needed particular technological developments. Among the most important concerns are the brittle inclusions, which are difficult to detect by non-destructive testing, and can initiate cracks and an early failure of the structures. Materials imperfections due to manufacturing process, for example, void and impurities develop flaws that can cause a material become weak [13].

Anderson [2] suggested using the stress-intensity factor to describe stress-corrosion crack propagation. During this time precracked specimens have been used increasingly in stress-corrosion testing, and the data interpreted in terms of linear elastic fracture mechanics.

A good review on the most relevant analytical, experimental and numerical works conducted in the three last decades and

related to the cracked structures behavior were reported by Dimarogonas and Paipetis [14,15], Gasch [15], El Arem [16].

Theoretical model calculation for stress intensity factor:

Plate with Edge crack

Consider a finite plate in tension with a central crack as shown in Fig. The plate is made of Ti-6Al-4V with Young's modulus $E=114.3$ GPa and Poisson's ratio $\nu=0.3$. Let $b=0.2m$, $a=0.2$: m , $\sigma=100MPa$. Determine the stress intensity factors [18, 19, and 20].

Crack length, $a = 0.02$ mm

Plate width, $b= 0.2$ mm

$$K_i = \sigma \sqrt{\pi a}$$

$$\eta = 0.02/0.2 = 0.1$$

$$c = (1 - 0.1(0.1)^2 + 0.96(0.1)^4) \sqrt{1/(\cos \pi)} = 0.86$$

$$K_i = 50.132 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{m}$$

Finite Element Modelling And Methodology

The methodology used to investigate the mechanics of crack propagation consists of the following steps:

- Model creation
- Elastic stress analysis of the un cracked body
- Flaw implementation
- Crack propagation
- Elastic stress analysis of the cracked body
- Calculation of stress intensity factor
- Interpretation of results

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stress Distribution in Un-notched Plate

Using the numerical package ANSYS, we also determined the value of the stress intensity factor K_I for the same geometry. This was computed using finite elements on a mesh with quadratic triangular elements on the vicinity of the crack tip, and quadratic rectangular elements everywhere else[13]. Quarter point elements, formed by placing the mid-side node near the crack tip at the quarter point, were used to account for the crack singularity. In Table 2 we display some values of K_I/K_0 , where $K_0 = \sigma \sqrt{\pi a}$, up to two significant digits. It can be seen that our results, identified by theoretical values by using of empirical formulas, are in line with those predicted by ANSYS, and even more so for smaller values of a/b . We further illustrate this analysis in Figure 5, for which more data points were taken.

Table1 stress intensity factors

	a/b= 0.1	a/b= 0.2	a/b= 0.4	a/b= 0.6	a/b= 0.8
ANSYS	1.01	1.1	1.28	1.50	2.03
Theoreti cal	1.01	1.07	1.23	1.48	1.98

As we had already mentioned, the stress intensity factor depends on the geometry of the plate we are considering. In particular, it depends on the ratio h/b . On Table 1 we display the values of K_I/K_0 , determined again using ANSYS, for different geometries.

Table2 values of K_I/K_0 for different geometries

	a/b= 0.1	a/b= 0.2	a/b= 0.4	a/b= 0.6	a/b= 0.8
h/b=0 .25	1.01	1.2	1.63	1.99	2.65
h/b=0 .5	1.12	1.3	1.8	2.42	3.77
h/b=1	1.14	1.5	1.92	2.97	4.03
h/b=2	1.18	1.6	2.01	3.57	4.65
h/b=∞	1.2	1.7	2.22	3.77	6.42

We note that as the value of h/b increases, the values of K_I/K_0 tend to the values of the last line ($h/b = \infty$), which refers to values that we would expect for an infinite stripe with a centre through crack under tension, as in Figure. To better illustrate this idea, we conclude with the graphical representations of the values of Table2.

Comparison of stress concentration Factor

Variation of KI/Ko for different geometries

CONCLUSIONS

This project investigated the process of crack propagation and the resulting stress distribution in a typical Ti-6Al-4V aerospace skin using ANSYS. The behaviour of corner cracks was studied since this type of flaw is most frequently encountered in practice. The first step of the analysis consisted of using ANSYS to perform elastic stress analysis on an existing un-notched skin to identify the high stress regions. In step two, the un-notched model was plotted in ANSYS, an initial crack of simple geometry was introduced and several ANSYS files were created with a re-meshed finite element structure around the crack. Step three of the analysis consisted of using ANSYS to perform elastic stress analysis of the notched skin. In step four, ANSYS was used again to compute the stress-intensity factor and to further extend the crack. Steps three and four were then repeated twice to obtain the results reported in the thesis. For the model of corner cracks, the results show that the Von Mises elastic static stress is above the yield strength for the two load cycles considered in this study. Under tensile loading condition the stress-intensity factors for the cracked model are below the material's fracture toughness. Therefore, it appears that the skin can tolerate small corner cracks in the structure.

Citation: D.Harsha Vardhan et al., (2014) Analysis on Crack Propagation in Ti-6al-4v Skin under Tensile Loading J. of Advancement in Engineering and Technology. V2I1. DOI: 10.15297/JAET.V2I1.03

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